

Paper 6

**A STUDY ON THE TYPE OF PERSONALITY AND TEACHING APTITUDE
OF STUDENT TEACHERS**

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ABSTRACT

Personality is the all-round development of the individual in all aspects like physical, intellectual, emotional, social, and mental characteristics. In the present 21st century it is necessary for the individual to develop good personality to adjust himself to the society. Personality characteristics developed in the individual through school or classroom which is considered as a miniature society. The teacher should help the students to develop good personality by motivating them to involve them in teaching learning process as well as through co-curricular activities. For this reason, student teachers need to have good personality to teach values of life. The present study intended to identify the type of personality and aptitude of student teachers towards teaching profession. The sample of the study was 100 student teachers, selected by random sampling method. A standardized tool Eyenseck personality inventory and teaching aptitude scale by Dr. Surender Dhayia and L.P Singh were used. The collected data was analysed by using statistical techniques namely Mean, SD, t-test and Karl Pearson's product moment correlation. The Major findings of the study revealed that a) 48.18 % of student teachers exhibit extrovert personality, 35.15 % of student teachers exhibits lie scale, 15.45% of student teachers exhibits neuroticism personality and only 0.09% of student teachers exhibit psychoticism personality, b) The study also indicated that only 3% of student teachers showed good teaching aptitude, 46% of student teachers showed average level, 48% of student teachers showed low level and 7% of student teachers showed poor level of teaching aptitude, c) Study also reveals that there is no significant relationship between personality and teaching aptitude of student teacher. There is no significant difference between urban and rural student teachers based on their personality. They do not differ in teaching aptitude in terms of Locality, stream of the students, and Gender. Some techniques are suggested to foster teaching aptitude and personality of student teachers in the study.

Key words: Personality, teaching aptitude, urban and rural student teachers, science and arts pedagogy student teachers

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Introduction:

The Education commission (1964-66) observes that education must serve as a powerful instrument of social, economic and cultural transformation necessary for the realization of the national goals. A teacher is an important part of any educational system. According H.G Well's "the teacher is the real make of history". Every profession requires a high level of teaching ability. Any teacher who does not have a significant amount of teaching aptitude will be unable to perform his or her duties properly, identifying the role of teaching aptitude in the teaching profession. The successful running of an secondary educational system depends upon mainly its teachers special ability, teachers adjustment, involvement, personality is main reason and teachers personality factors of education should be in tune with time and needs of society. "Personality as a stable and enduring combination of a person's various physical and mental aspects",

The word 'aptitude' is derived from the word 'Aptos', which means 'fitted 'for'. The term aptitude is differently defined by different psychologists, as many cases do happen, but these different definitions agree in certain essentials such as 'present ability', 'role of training', 'case of acquiring proficiency', 'interest in activity' and so on. In the Dictionary of Education (Good, 1959), aptitude is defined 'as a pronounced innate capacity for or ability in a given line of Endeavour such as a particular art, school subject or vocation'. Thus in this definition, an aptitude refers to an individuals' inborn capacities or potentialities which are indicative of some special abilities In the Dictionary of Education (Good, 1959), aptitude is defined 'as a pronounced innate capacity for or ability in a given line of Endeavour such as a particular art, school subject or vocation'. Thus in this definition, an aptitude refers to an individuals' inborn capacities or potentialities which are indicative of some special abilities. Along with teaching aptitude personality of the teacher also plays an important role. According to Cattell R.B (1967) "Personality is that which permits a prediction of what a person will do in a given situation." Eysenck H.J. (1947): views personality "as a stable and enduring combination of a person's various physical and mental aspects".

Need for the study:

The teachers are at the centre of everything in the educational system. Teachers' qualities and flaws leave an indelible mark on the minds of future generations. The teacher plays a crucial role in educational systems.

Teacher is at the centre of the process and is the only one who can "Mend or End" the individual, society, and nation's fixation. However, a teacher's thoughts, feelings, and actions are influenced by his personality and teaching aptitude. Teachers' personality and teaching aptitude are the most important spheres of their behaviour in the field of education, and they are critical for an effective teaching-learning process. Thus, to some extent, effective teaching is the result of a teacher's personality and teaching ability. When compared to rural school teachers, the general public believes that private school teachers have a positive personality and excellent teaching abilities. As a result, the current research aims to compare the personalities and teaching abilities of urban and

rural student teachers. There is general public opinion that urban Student teachers have good personality and high teaching aptitude as compared to rural school teachers. As a result, the current research aims to compare the personalities and teaching abilities of rural and urban student teachers. This research will yield useful information that will aid in the re-framing of teacher education programmes. In the present study current research has direct implications for educational systems, particularly for those involved in teacher education.

Statement of the problem

A STUDY ON THE TYPE OF PERSONALITY AND TEACHING APTITUDE OF B.ED STUDENT TEACHERS

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The main objectives of the study are:

1. To study the type of personality of student teachers
2. To study the aptitude of student teachers towards teaching profession
3. To study if there is any significant relationship between personality and teaching aptitude among student teachers
4. To study if there is any difference between urban and rural student teachers on their personality
5. To study if there is any significant difference between urban and rural student teachers on their teaching aptitude.
6. To study if there is any significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their personality
7. To study if there is any significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their teaching aptitude

Hypotheses of the study:

- H₀1:** There is no significant relationship between personality and teaching aptitude of student teachers.
- H₀2:** There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers on their Personality.
- H₀3:** There is no significant difference between rural and urban student teachers on their teaching aptitude
- H₀4:** There is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their personality
- H₀5:** There is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their teaching

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aptitude

Limitation of the study:

The present investigation has following limitation

1. The study was restricted to only student teachers of Srinivas University.
2. The sample size was restricted to only 100 student teachers.

Methodology:

To achieve the objectives of the study researcher used survey method of descriptive research. Variables of the present study comprise personality, teaching aptitude rural and urban student teachers and combination of subject (science and arts).

Sample size:

The researcher used simple random sampling method. The researcher has selected 110 samples out of which 50 student teachers from urban and 60 student teachers from rural of Srinivas University.

Tools used:

The researcher used standardised eyenseck personality questionnaire and teaching aptitude scale by Dr.Surender Dhayia and L.P Singh

Data collection:

Researcher after selecting the standardized tool data is collected through Google forms by sending the links to the B.Ed student teachers

Statistical technique used:

The following statistical techniques were used for analysis and interpretation of data

Analysis of the data:

Data was collected from science and arts pedagogy student teachers of Srinivas University. The student teachers are provided with a standardized eyenseck personality questionnaire and teaching aptitude scale. The researcher used questionnaire method to measure the personality and teaching aptitude of student teachers they were given sufficient time to answer. The response sheet was then collected through Google forms.

Results of the study:

1. To study the type of personality of student teachers

Table 1: Type of Personality

Type of Personality	Number of students	Percentage of students
Extrovert	50	48.07
Lie scale	36	34.61
Neuroticism	15	14.42
Psychoticism	3	2.88

The results revealed that 48.07 percent of student teachers exhibits Extroverts personality (E), 34.61 percent of student teachers exhibits Lie scale (L), 14.42 percent of student teachers exhibits Neuroticism personality and 2.88 percent of student teachers exhibits Psychoticism personality (P).

2. To study the aptitude of student teachers towards teaching profession

Table 1 Aptitude of student teachers towards teaching profession.

Standard score	Level of Aptitude	Number of student
61 – 55.17	good	3
55.17 – 47.40	average	46
47.37- 33.73	low	48
Below 33.73	poor	7

The results reveal that 3% student teachers exhibit good level of teaching aptitude, 46 % student teachers exhibit average level of teaching aptitude, 48% student teachers exhibits low level of teaching aptitude and 7% student teachers exhibits poor level of aptitude towards teaching

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profession.

3. There is no significant relationship between personality and teaching aptitude among student teachers

Table 2. Personality and teaching aptitude

Categories	number	Correlation ‘r’ value
Personality	100	0.116
Teaching aptitude		

Table 1 show that the correlation value (r) of personality and teaching aptitude of student teachers was found to be 0.116 which is less than the table value at 0.05 significant levels. Hence null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that there is no significant relation between the personality and teaching aptitude of student teachers.

4. There is no significant difference between urban and rural student teachers on their personality

Table 3 . Urban and Rural student teachers on their personality

categories	Mean	Standard deviation	‘t’ value
Urban	22.98	3.29	0.661
Rural	22.5	3.94	

The table 2 shows that the mean and standard deviation of Urban and Rural student teachers on their personality are found to be 22.98 (m) and 3.29 (S.D) and 22.5 (m) and 3.94 (S.D) respectively and the ‘t’ value is found to be 0.661 which is less than the table value at 0.05 significant levels. The null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between Urban and Rural student teachers on their personality.

5. There is no significant difference between urban and rural student teachers on their teaching aptitude

Table 4. Urban and Rural student teachers and their teaching aptitude

Categories	Mean	Standard Deviation	‘t’ value
Urban	30.96	6.51	-0.44
Rural	31.5	5.71	

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The table 4 shows that the mean and standard deviation of Urban and Rural student teachers on their teaching aptitude are found to be 30.96 (m) and 6.51 (S.D) and 31.5 (m) and 5.71 (S.D) respectively and the ‘t’ value is found to be -0.44 which is less than the table value at 0.05 significant levels. The null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between Urban and Rural student teachers on their teaching aptitude.

6. There is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their personality

Table 5. Science and Arts student teachers on their personality

Categories	Mean	Standard Deviation	‘t’ value
Science	23.32	3.19	0.412
Arts	23.02	3.37	

The table 5 shows that the mean and standard deviation of science and arts students are found to be 23.32 (m) and 3.91 (S.D) and 23.02 (m) and 3.37 (S.D) respectively and the ‘t’ value is found to be 0.412 which is less than the table value at 0.05 significant levels. The null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their personality.

7. There is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their teaching aptitude

Table 6. Science and arts student teachers on their teaching aptitude

Categories	Mean	Standard Deviation	‘t’ value
Science	31.16	5.49	0.191
Arts	30.90	6.51	

The table 6 shows that the mean and standard deviation of science and arts students are found to be 31.16 (m) and 5.49 (S.D) and 30.90 (m) and 6.51 (S.D) respectively and the ‘t’ value is found to be 0.191 which is less than the table value at 0.05 significant levels. The null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their teaching aptitude.

Finding of the study:

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1. The type of personality of student teachers 48.18 percent of student teachers were found to be Extrovert personality (E), 35.45 percent of student teachers were found to be Lie scale (L), 15.45 percent of student teachers were found to be Neuroticism personality and 0.09 percent of student teachers were found to be Psychoticism personality (P).
2. The aptitude of student teachers towards teaching profession is found in such a way that 3% student teachers exhibits good level of teaching aptitude, 46% student teachers exhibits average level of teaching aptitude, 48% of student teachers exhibits low level of teaching aptitude and 7% of student teachers exhibits poor level of teaching aptitude .
3. There is no significant relationship between personality and teaching aptitude among student teachers.
4. There is no significant difference between urban and rural student teachers on their personality.
5. There is no significant difference between urban and rural student teachers on their teaching aptitude
6. There is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their personality.
7. There is no significant difference between science and arts student teachers on their teaching aptitude.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The following are the implications drawn out from the findings of the present study.

1. The findings may provide recommendations to curriculum developers for developing a suitable curriculum for student-teachers in order to develop a positive personality and aptitude for teaching.
2. According to the findings, teacher training programmes aid in the development of teaching skills, so no one should be allowed to teach in schools without a B.Ed.
3. It measures the aptitude of student teachers towards teaching profession and personality by using standardized tools.
4. The study also assesses the amount of training given from college of teacher education for student teachers to become effective teachers.
5. It aids in viewing teaching aspects from a psychological perspective, such as teaching aptitude and personality.

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6. It strengthens the research by using psychological tools to assess the level of teaching aptitude and personality among students in teacher education colleges.
7. To overcome a student's hesitations and open up while expressing an answer or clarifying a doubt, awareness can be developed.
8. It entails a long-term retention programme that counteracts out-of-date or ineffective instruction. It can be said that they will not be competitive in teaching in their content subject unless they are dedicated to the teaching fields.
9. The study found no significant differences in aptitude between rural and urban teacher trainees. As a result, it can be concluded that both teachers are equally capable of teaching in schools.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDY:

1. A comparative study on teaching can be done among the graduates with and without a diploma in education i.e. the graduates who are trained in colleges of education with that of graduates who are not trained.
2. A study can be done to measure the skills and efforts in utilizing local resources to demonstrate the lessons to show their teaching aptitude.
3. A study can be conducted to determine appropriate methods for assessing the effects of specific learning and knowledge accounts.
4. Identical studies can be pursued separately for the Government and private colleges of student teachers
5. A comparative study of the same primary variables among Male and female college students of education can be conducted.

Conclusion:

Teaching is more than just a way to make a living; it is also a path to perfection. The fate of a nation and society is largely determined by education, and teachers must play a significant role in making it more sustainable and effective. Teaching is a dynamic process that must be improved in response to changing societal and student needs and demands, and in order to improve the quality of teachers, an updated and rigorous aptitude is required, along with all other necessary ingredients such as personality, knowledge, intelligence, and communication. Based on the findings, it can be

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concluded that teacher training programmes are essential for becoming professionally skilled teachers because they aid in the development of positive personality traits and aptitude for teaching. Teacher education could be tailored to help teachers develop the mindsets and skills they need to meet the challenges they face in the classroom.

Bibliography:

Rani, Shallu (2021). A Study of Teaching Aptitude among B.ED Students. **International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR) - Peer Reviewed Journal**, 7(3), 123-128. ISSN (Online): 2455-3662

Mahakul Deepak. IMPARTING ART EDUCATION THROUGH FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE (FOSS): AN EXPERIMENT WITH SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. **International Education and Research Journal**, 4(2), 1-3

Das Jharna (2021). A Study Of Teaching Aptitude among the Trainee Teachers in WEST BENGAL. **International Journal on Creative Research Thoughts**, 9(2), 531-536

Kaur Harmeeth (2014). A Comparative Study of Teaching Aptitude. *Indian journal of Research* perpix 3(8), 28-30.

Kumar Sharath. C.R.(2018). A Study of Type of Personality and Aptitude of B.Ed Teacher Trainees of Mysore city. **International education and research journal**, 4(2), 15-16.

Gondhi Sadhana. M (2015). A Study of Teaching Aptitude of Secondary school Teachers in relation to their job satisfaction social adjustment and personality Factors.

Khundare Harishchandra Surekha, Ghoti.R.M (2019). A study of achievement motivation, self – concept and adjustment among college students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(2), 825-828.
